
Predicting the Influence of Factors Affecting Consumer Acceptance on Startups in the Proposed Open Network for Digital Commerce– A Study

Abishiha Gracelyn Augustine
Student, Department of Commerce,
Madras Christian College, Chennai.

Dr. T. Shirley Devakirubai
Assistant Professor & Research Supervisor,
Department of Commerce, Madras Christian College, Chennai,
E-mail: shirleydevakirubai@mcc.edu.in

A b s t r a c t

The Open Source for Digital Commerce (ONDC) aims to democratise e-commerce. This study explores the motivating and demotivating factors that influence customer acceptance of startups in ONDC. Using a combination of approaches that involve qualitative and quantitative research, the study indicates a strong relationship between motivating factors and transaction intentions, emphasising the potential of ONDC to transform digital commerce. To encourage wider adoption, usability and security concerns must be resolved. Although this research acknowledges the limitations of demographic representation, it also emphasises the need for further study on technological and cultural barriers. This study recommends extensive awareness initiatives, improved security measures, and focused marketing strategies to encourage ONDC adoption. Furthermore, the study provides valuable insights into startups in the network that enables them to make informed decisions, mitigate risks, and seize opportunities in ONDC.

Keywords: ONDC, Startups, Consumer Adoption, Digital Commerce, E-Commerce, Technological Barriers, Cultural Barriers, Marketing Strategies, Security Measures, Informed Decisions

1. Introduction

The emergence of e-commerce has transformed the way businesses interact with their consumers; nevertheless, a large number of platforms have minimised their actual scope. In recent years, platform-centric business models that serve as middlemen between customers and sellers have been developed, such as Amazon and Flipkart. 'ONDC has the potential to be a game-changer for e-commerce in India, but its success will depend on careful planning and execution' (Ram Girdhar). India's Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) defies this convention by promoting an open-network ecosystem. Using an open-source methodology, ONDC promotes accessibility and transparency, thereby facilitating smooth transactions across numerous platforms and removing the need for users to explore several markets. 'ONDC is projected to digitise the whole value chain, standardise processes, encourage supplier inclusion, improve logistics efficiency, and increase consumer value' (Bibhu Dash). To estimate future market acceptance, this study looks at consumer behaviour across demographics, highlighting the need to resolve customer concerns for widespread adoption. In addition, it provides guidance on how companies can efficiently explore and take advantage of ONDC's potential. 'ONDC aims to make e-commerce procedures open source, thus creating a platform that can be utilized by all online retailers.' (Shaji George)

• PURCHASE INTENTION IN THE ONDC: MOTIVATION FACTORS

1. Convenience
2. Product Variety
3. Purchase Surrounding
4. Information Depth
5. Brand

• CONCERNS FOR ONDC: DEMOTIVATING FACTORS:

1. Risk:
2. Economic considerations
3. Conditions and Ability
4. Time and Socialization
5. Users' sensory experiences and decision-making processes

2. Literature Review

Amit Bhatnagar (2000) demonstrates how people still find the Internet risky compared to its convenience. Managers of online stores should focus on reducing these perceived risks, such as making connections more secure and addressing product concerns. Tailored strategies based on gender, marital status, and age can help. However, the study has some limitations, such as not including those who do not use the Internet. It also acknowledges that as technology advances, people's views may change. Their study emphasises the understanding of how risk and convenience influence people's choices between online and traditional stores, raising the question of what financial risk level would make the Internet a strong competitor of traditional outlets.

Anita Walia (2023) talks about ONDC, a technology-driven system supporting small businesses in smart digital commerce. It has shifted

from a platform-focused approach to an open-source setup that connects sellers and customers smoothly. Security is a major concern owing to data theft fears. Price is also vital, and ONDC stands out for speeding up discovery, cutting out middlemen, and offering competitive pricing. Trust is crucial for sellers and customers. To build trust, this study recommends a big awareness campaign by the Indian government regarding the ONDC benefits.

Baumeister (2002) explored how perceived usefulness is a key motivator for buying in an open market, saving time and money for both sellers and buyers. According to Technology Accepted Model, it directly influences purchase intentions in the open network market, combining rational and economic assessments with emotional values tied to social dimensions. This creates a dynamic platform for transactions between buyers and sellers. Stern's 1962 study points out that low prices, many choices, mass advertising, and prominent store displays strongly influence online market purchases in a self-service setting.

Nurul Nadia Abd Aziz (2018) looks at why some people don't shop online and finds that worries about product quality and privacy are key concerns. This suggests that online stores can improve by addressing these concerns through better designs and customer support. Their study also notes that traditional stores still have a place, offering a fun experience and unique services. Understanding these reasons is crucial for digital marketing strategies and the effective use of websites and social media. The findings help fill research gaps, shedding light on why some prefer traditional shopping and are hesitant to buy online, thus improving our overall understanding of this area.

Sang Soo Kim (2020) explores why people shop online and how certain things affect their decisions. The findings show that saving money and time and finding it easy to use makes people more likely to buy online. Concerns about privacy negatively affect the connection between time saving, ease of use, and buying intention. Surprisingly, privacy concerns positively influenced the link between saving money and buying intention. Security concerns also negatively impact the relationship between saving money and buying intention. However, business integrity concerns do not significantly impact saving money and have an unexpected positive effect on the link between timesaving and buying intention.

3. Significance of the Study

This study is crucial for understanding the dynamics of customer acceptability within the ONDC framework, as it sheds light on the factors that determine the success of startups in this ecosystem. Investigating motivating and demotivating factors provides useful insights for administrators and entrepreneurs seeking to capitalize on ONDC's revolutionary potential.

4. Statement of Problem

The introduction of ONDC represents a paradigm shift in the e-commerce environment, but its success depends on consumer

acceptance and the competitiveness of startups on the platform. The purpose of this study is to determine the key factors impacting consumer acceptance as well as the implications for startups in the ONDC network. Addressing these aspects is critical for promoting widespread adoption and long-term growth within the network.

5. Need for the Study

This study highlights the pressing need to fully understand the factors influencing consumer acceptance and startup performance in this network. By addressing this requirement, this study intends to provide stakeholders with actionable information for overcoming barriers, optimising tactics, and fostering long-term growth within the ONDC network. Finally, this study aims to contribute to the realisation of ONDC's revolutionary vision of digital commerce in India.

6. Research Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data were collected through a questionnaire. The sample size of the study was limited to 200. Convenience sampling was used for data collection. In this study, the SPSS statistical tool was adopted for analysis purposes. The following tests were used for analysis purposes.

- One-Sample T-Test
- Independent Sample T-Test
- One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)
- Chi-Square tests
- Test for Significance of Correlation Coefficient.

6.1 Objectives of the Study

- To investigate the influence of motivating factors on consumer acceptance of startups in ONDC.
- To identify the influence of demotivating factors hindering consumer acceptance of startups in ONDC and potential solutions to address these concerns.
- To assess how these factors affect the purchase intention of ONDC consumers.

6.2 Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between males and females with respect to motivating/demotivating factors affecting the Purchase Intention of Consumers.
2. There is no significant difference among different age groups with respect to motivating/ demotivating factors affecting the Purchase Intention of Consumers
3. There is no association between consumers' intention to try ONDC in the near future and their age, education, and location.
4. There is no significant correlation between motivating/demotivating factors and the transaction intention of consumers.

6.3 Limitations of the Study

1. The study did not fully represent all demographics, especially older

age groups or certain socioeconomic backgrounds.

2. Other crucial factors, such as technological and cultural barriers, have not been fully explored.
3. External factors that could affect online purchasing behaviour, such as competitive markets, laws, or economic conditions, were not explored in the study.
4. In the long term, the dynamics of consumer behaviour and e-commerce may differ, which this study does not explore.

7. Data Analysis and Interpretation

i) One-Sample T-Test for Motivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Table 4.27 One-Sample T-Test for Motivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Factors	Mean	SD	t value	p value	Rank
Cost-Savings	10.97	1.616	95.989	<0.001	2
Time-Savings	10.98	1.585	97.970	<0.001	1
Perceived Ease of Use	7.32	1.164	88.952	<0.001	3

Interpretation:

The results reveal that all three motivating factors of purchase intention, Cost-Savings, Time-Savings, and Perceived Ease of Use, have a statistically significant impact on the purchase intention of consumers. With a mean score of 10.98 and 10.97, time-saving and cost-saving hold the highest priority, respectively. This was followed by perceived ease of use, with a mean score of 7.32. These factors play a crucial role in influencing consumers' purchase decisions.

ii) One-Sample T-Test for Demotivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Table 4.28 One-Sample T-Test for Motivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Factors	Mean	SD	t value	p value	Rank
Privacy	7.37	1.153	90.385	<0.001	1
Security	7.25	1.181	86.826	<0.001	2
Trust	7.03	1.175	84.532	<0.001	3

Interpretation: The results reveal that all three demotivating factors of purchase intention – Privacy, Security, and Trust – have statistically significant impacts on the purchase intention of consumers. With a mean score of 7.37 and 7.25, privacy and security hold the highest priority, respectively. This was followed by trust, with a mean score of 7.03. These factors play a crucial role in influencing consumers’ purchase decisions.

Independent Sample T-Test

Factors affecting consumers’ purchase intentions were impacted by the research study based on their gender. The results will be established through an Independent Sample T-Test, which is given below:

i) Independent Sample T-Test for Motivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Table 4.29: t-test for significant difference between Male and Female with respect to Motivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Factors	Gender				t value	p value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cost-Savings	11.25	0.968	10.73	1.984	2.285	0.023
Time-Savings	11.25	0.979	10.75	1.934	2.246	0.026
Perceived Ease of Use	7.54	0.619	7.13	1.454	2.541	0.012
Total	30.04	2.143	28.61	5.132	2.498	0.013

Interpretation: The findings suggest that there is a significant difference between male and female consumers with regard to the motivating factors of purchase intention (t = 2.498, p = 0.013). The P value of 0.013 was less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 5% level with regard to the motivating factors affecting purchase intention. This implies that the observed variations in the motivating factors between genders are statistically significant, suggesting that gender does play a significant role in motivating purchase intention among consumers.

ii) Independent Sample T-Test for Demotivating Factors of Purchase Intention

Table 4.3: t-test for significant difference between Male and Female with respect to Demotivating Factors of Purchase Intention.

Factors	Gender				t value	p value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Privacy	7.54	0.619	7.22	1.449	1.978	0.049
Security	7.52	0.763	7.02	1.407	3.066	0.002
Trust	7.18	0.937	6.89	1.335	1.784	0.076
Total	22.25	1.419	21.13	3.676	2.753	0.006

Interpretation: The findings suggest that there is a significant difference between male and female consumers with regard to the demotivating factors of purchase intention (t = 2.753, p = 0.006). The P value of 0.006 was less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 5% level with regard to the demotivating factors affecting purchase intention. This implies that the observed variations in the demotivating factors between genders are statistically significant, suggesting that gender does play a significant role in hindering purchase intention among consumers.

ANOVA: The factors affecting consumers’ purchase intention were impacted by the research study based on their age group. The results will be established through One-way Analysis of Variance, which is given below:

Impact of Age on Factors of Purchase Intention

Table 4.31: ANOVA for significant difference among age groups with respect to motivating factors of purchase intention of consumers:

Motivating Factors	Age				F value	P value
	18-24	25-34	35-55	Above 55		
Cost-saving	11.32 (0.698)	9.79 (2.859)	11.31 (0.655)	10.92 (1.847)	11.261	<0.001**
Time-saving	11.29 (0.743)	9.88 (2.787)	11.31 (0.655)	11.00 (1.871)	9.812	<0.001**
Perceived Ease of Use	7.56 (0.536)	6.48 (2.075)	7.56 (0.641)	7.38 (0.870)	10.795	<0.001**
Overall Total	30.17 (1.363)	26.24 (7.511)	30.18 (1.335)	29.31 (4.404)	12.301	<0.001**

Interpretation:

The data show that consumers' perceptions of the motivational factors for purchase intention differ significantly by age group. Compared to older age groups, younger age groups—especially those between the ages of 18 and 24—tend to give more importance to features that save money and time and are perceived as being easier to use.

Table 4.32: ANOVA for significant difference among age groups with respect to demotivating factors of purchase intention of consumers:

Demotivating Factors	Age				F value	P value
	18-24	25-34	35-55	Above 55		
Privacy Concern	7.59 (0.644)	6.62 (2.048)	7.46 (0.643)	7.69 (0.480)	8.574	<0.001**
Security Concern	7.40 (0.801)	6.69 (1.944)	7.36 (0.873)	7.54 (0.877)	4.253	0.006**
Trust	7.24 (0.879)	6.31 (1.760)	7.10 (0.912)	7.38 (0.768)	7.448	<0.001**
Overall Total	22.23 (1.423)	19.62 (5.282)	21.92 (1.596)	22.62 (1.121)	9.944	<0.001**

Interpretation: The data show that consumers' views of demotivating factors connected to purchase intention are highly influenced by age. Older age groups, particularly those over 55, tend to be more concerned about privacy, security, and trust in online transactions than younger age groups.

Chi-Square Test: Association between consumers' intention to try ONDC in the near future and their age.

Table 4.37: Cross-tabulation of transaction intention and age

Transaction Intention	Age				Total
	18-24 years (%)	25-34 years (%)	35-54 years (%)	Above 55 years (%)	
Very Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	4 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	4 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Likely	23 (63.9%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (13.9%)	4 (11.0%)	36 (100.0%)
Very Likely	83 (53.2%)	30 (19.2%)	34 (21.8%)	9 (5.8%)	156 (100.0%)
Total	106 (53%)	42 (21.0%)	39 (19.5%)	13 (6.5%)	200 (100.0%)

From the above table, it is found that 53.2% of the consumers who are very likely to try ONDC belong to the age group of 18-24 years, and 63.9% of the consumers who are likely to try ONDC are also from the age group of 18-24 years. It is also found that consumers who are unlikely or very unlikely to try ONDC belong to the age group of 25-34 years. This leads to the computation of chi-square statistics, as shown in the table below.

Table 4.38: Showing Chi-square Tests for transaction intention and age

Computed Statistics	Value	df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35.119 ^a	9	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	30.148	9	<.001
Linear – by – Linear Association	0.032	1	0.858
N of Valid Cases	200		

From the above table, it is found that Pearson chi-square = 35.119a, p=<0.001 is statistically significant. There is a strong association between consumers' transaction intentions and their age. The data indicate that age is an important variable that has a significant role in **influencing the transaction intention of consumers.**

Association between consumers' intention to try ONDC in the near future and their education.

Table 4.39: Cross-tabulation of transaction intention and education

Transaction Intention	Education			Total
	High School	Undergraduate	Postgraduate	
Very Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Likely	2 (5.6%)	26 (72.2%)	8 (22.2%)	36 (100.0%)
Very Likely	2 (1.3%)	95 (60.9%)	59 (37.8%)	156 (100.0%)
Total	4 (100.0%)	121 (60.5%)	75 (37.5%)	200 (100.0%)

From the above table, it is found that 60.9% of the consumers who are very likely to try ONDC have completed an undergraduate degree, and 72.2% of the consumers who are likely to try ONDC have also completed an undergraduate degree. It is also found that consumers who are unlikely or very unlikely to try ONDC have completed their postgraduate degree. This leads to the computation of chi-square statistics, as shown in the table below.

Table 4.40: Chi-square tests for transaction intention and education

Computed Statistics	Value	Df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.078 ^a	6	0.004
Likelihood Ratio	21.087	6	0.002
Linear – by – Linear Association	1.916	1	0.166
N of Valid Cases	200		

From the above table, it is found that Pearson chi-square = 19.078a, p=0.004 is statistically significant. There is a strong association between consumers' transaction intentions and their education. The data indicate that education is an important variable that has a significant role in influencing the transaction intention of consumers.

Association between consumers' intention to try ONDC in the near future and their location

Table 4.41: Cross-tabulation of transaction intention and location

Transaction Intention	Location			Total
	Urban	Suburban	Rural	
Very Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Unlikely	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	4 (100.0%)
Likely	20 (55.6%)	13 (36.1%)	3 (8.3%)	36 (100.0%)
Very Likely	87 (55.8%)	49 (31.4%)	20 (12.8%)	156 (100.0%)
Total	107 (53.5%)	62 (31.0%)	31 (15.5%)	200 (100.0%)

From the above table, it is found that 53.5% of the consumers who are very likely to try ONDC belong to urban areas, and 55.6% of the consumers who are likely to try ONDC are also from Urban areas. It is also found that consumers who are unlikely or very unlikely to try ONDC belong to rural areas. This leads to the computation of chi-square statistics, as shown in the table below.

Table 4.42: Showing Chi-square Tests for transaction intention and Location

Computed Statistics	Value	Df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46.019 ^a	6	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	32.507	6	<0.001
Linear – by – Linear Association	14.866	1	<0.001
N of Valid Cases	200		

From the above table, it is found that Pearson chi-square = 46.019a, p<0.001 is statistically significant. There is a strong association between consumers’ transaction intention and their location. The data indicate that location is an important variable that has a significant role in influencing the transaction intention of consumers.

Test for Significance of Correlation Coefficient

Table 4.43: Karl Pearson Correlation Coefficient between Motivating Factors of Consumers’ Transaction Interpretation:

Perceived cost savings (r = 0.590, p < 0.01), time savings (r = 0.604, p < 0.01), and perceived ease of use (r = 0.658, p < 0.01) were all positively correlated with users’ intention to transact. This suggests that users are more likely to transact when they believe they are saving time and money and when they find the platform easy to use. Transaction intention and privacy concerns had a positive correlation (r = 0.649, p < 0.01), suggesting that users prioritized privacy while choosing platforms. Transaction intention and security concerns also showed a moderate correlation (r = 0.473, p < 0.01), indicating that individuals are more inclined to transact on platforms that they believe are safe. Furthermore, there was a positive correlation (r = 0.478, p < 0.01) between transaction intention and platform trust, suggesting that trust affects users’ tendency to transact. Strong positive correlations between perceived ease of use, cost-saving, and time-saving (0.726** and 0.712**, respectively) have also been observed.

8. Findings of the Study

- The respondents mentioned positive experiences: 27.5% were satisfied, and 18% were very satisfied. Neutral responses (31.5%) indicated an openness to new platforms, although dissatisfaction (18%) presented the potential for improved insights.
- Occasional participation (50.5%) implies that respondents regularly use online shopping. Regular participation (29.5%) indicates that a sizable percentage appreciated the convenience of Internet buying.
- A significant portion of the population is still uninformed (56%) despite growing knowledge of ONDC (31%), underscoring the necessity of awareness initiatives. Effective communication platforms are indicated by the significant role that online media channels play in educating people about ONDC.
- The respondents had a significant knowledge gap, with the majority claiming a low to extremely low understanding. It emphasises the importance of developing ways to bridge this gap and increase awareness.
- Online buying is primarily motivated by the importance of cost (66%) and time-saving (69%) considerations. The effectiveness and ease of use of online platforms were evaluated as crucial factors, with a focus on customer preferences.
- The results reveal that all three demotivating factors of purchase intention – Privacy, Security, and Trust – have statistically significant impacts on the purchase intention of consumers.
- The findings suggest that there is a significant difference between male and female consumers regarding the motivating factors of purchase intention.
- There is a significant difference between male and female consumers about the demotivating factors of purchase intention.
- There is a positive correlation between motivating factors (cost savings, time savings, perceived ease of use) and transaction

intentions. Similarly, there are positive relationships

- between demotivating characteristics (privacy, security, and trust) and transaction intent. Consumers tend to actively choose platforms that address their concerns and provide easy and safe transaction experiences. Consumers' perceptions of motivational factors for purchase intention differed significantly by age group. Consumers' views of the demotivating factors connected to purchase intention are highly influenced by age.
- There is a strong association between consumers' transaction intentions and their age. It was found that 60.9% of the consumers who are very likely to try ONDC have completed an undergraduate degree, and 72.2% of the consumers who are likely to try ONDC have also completed an undergraduate degree.
- There is a strong association between consumers' transaction intention and their location.

9. Suggestions

- Launch extensive awareness campaigns to educate the public about the features and benefits of ONDC, particularly regarding online platforms.
- Give top priority to improving ONDC's security measures to reassure users and foster trust. Provide clear instructions on how to use ONDC safely, particularly for those who are not used to online transactions.
- Constant work to enhance ONDC's usability and efficiency for customers.
- Tailor marketing campaigns to target particular demographics, such as younger people, those with lower levels of education, or those belonging to rural areas.
- Ensure that ONDC continues to be supported and promoted by the government. Establish feedback channels to collect data and improve ONDC based on user experience.
- Collaborate with MSMEs, retailers, and other stakeholders to better align ONDC with their needs and preferences.

10. Future Research

- A detailed study can be carried out on a larger scale to study the customer attitude and behavior towards ONDC.
- Further research on customer preference towards ONDC.
- More Variables on motivating/Demotivating factors can be included in the study.

11. Conclusion: Significant aspects of customer behavior and attitudes toward the Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) are highlighted in this study. This emphasises how revolutionary digital commerce may be with ONDC, particularly for small firms. However, customer acceptance depends on resolving important concerns, including usability, cost, and safety.

Demographics, such as location, age, gender, and education, also influence consumer attitudes, requiring specific marketing efforts.

Building trust requires addressing privacy and security issues while simultaneously boosting ease of use. transaction intentions through platform features that align with customer preferences, such as cost savings and In short, responding to consumer concerns and evolving along with the market are vital for startups under the ONDC network.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Funding

The authors received no funding support

References

- Amit Bhatnagar, Sanjog Misra, H Raghav Rao on the paper "On Risk, Convenience, and Internet Shopping Behaviour", Association for Computing Machinery. Communications of the ACM, November 2002
- Anita Walia, Dr. Varalakshmi, Dr. Kiran Lokesh Maney, on the paper, "Predicting Consumer Acceptance of the Proposed Open Network for Digital Commerce", IRE Journals, March 2023
- Baumeister on the paper, "Yielding to Temptation: Self-Control Failure, Impulsive Purchasing, and Consumer Behaviour", University of Michigan, Chicago Journals, September 2002.
- Bibhu Dash, Pawan Kumar Sharma, Meraj F Ansari, and Swati Swayamsidha on the paper, "A Review of ONDC's digital warfare in India taking on the e-commerce giants", International Journal of Engineering and Technology, January 2023.
- Nurul Nadia Abd Aziz, Normilia Abd Wahid, on the paper, "Why Consumers are Hesitant to Shop Online: The Major Concerns towards Online Shopping", International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, September 2018
- Ram Girdhar on the paper, "The Critical Analysis of Open Network For Digital Commerce In India", Kalinga University, Raipur C.G, April 2023
- Sang Soo Kim on the paper, "Purchase Intention in the Online Open Market: Do Concerns for E-Commerce Really Matter?" MDPI, Yong In University, January 2020
- Shaji George, A.S. Hovan George on the paper "Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) : Democratizing Digital Commerce and curbing digital monopolies in India", Partners Universal International Universal Research Journal, 2022